

Transient Global Amnesia as a Clue to Undiagnosed COVID-19: A Case Report

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Citation: Daryuş Heydari, Ayli Heydari, Çağdaş Kaya. *Transient Global Amnesia as a Clue to Undiagnosed COVID-19: A Case Report. Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour. 2024;3(8):1-8.*

Received Date: 22 August, 2024; **Accepted Date:** 25 August, 2024; **Published Date:** 26 August, 2024

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ABSTRACT

This is a novel report as it is one of the first cases of COVID-19 patients presenting with TGA. This patient was diagnosed with TGA at first, leading to the suspicion of COVID-19, which initially tested negative but later was found to be positive.

A 73-year-old woman was referred to the neurology outpatient clinic with complaints of fatigue, disorientation, and sudden memory loss and presented with transient global amnesia (TGA) symptoms.

Since November 2019, the first outbreak of COVID-19, world health has been challenged by many complications. Over the past three years, a lot of details about this virus and how it affects the body have come to light, but many concerns remain.

With this article, we aim to facilitate the diagnosis of future cases of COVID-19 presenting with TGA, as it shows the possibility of COVID-19 causing TGA.

Keywords: Transient Global Amnesia; COVID-19; TGA; EEG Abnormalities

INTRODUCTION

TGA is known to be a transitory state where the patient loses self-awareness. It is an "acute onset anterograde amnesia" that mostly affects the middle-aged, and it is known to be a clinical syndrome classified as a transient ischemic attack. The patients' alertness, focus, and cognition are usually unaffected.^[1,2,3]

It is well known that patients typically retain their sense of self, even if they frequently appear to ask questions over and over again and are frequently ignorant of their surroundings or the time or place.

TGA is seen in roughly 5.2–10/100,000 people in the general population annually. The incidence rises to 23.5 to 32/100,000 people over 50 years of age each year. In various reports, the mean age of patients varies between 50 and 80. No gender-specific differences exist.^[1]

This incidence has increased, as reported in some articles about the COVID-19 and SARS-CoV-2 virus outbreaks. However, some think this higher occurrence may be brought on by stress and the anxiety of being infected.

Some believe that the virus itself is what causes TGA, either directly by infecting the CNS or through an "encephalitic autoimmune disease."^[4]

Some articles have reported TGA incidence after COVID-19 vaccination. However, the exact reason or pathophysiology is not certain yet, and some articles have stated their own experience in this field.

In a study of 852 cases of TGA, it was shown that 289 cases were significantly related to the COVID-19 vaccine, and 178 of them were in serious condition. Women were reported to be affected more than men. Based on this report, the median age was 66 among the patients.^[5]

TGA was a complication of the disease itself in our case, although it generally may happen as a side effect of vaccination.

Generally, the adverse effects after the vaccination can be summarized as headaches, local pain, fatigue, nausea, and common neurological side effects occurring in 50% of the cases.^[6]

The hippocampus is known to be the origin of TGA. A watershed region of the brain, the hippocampus is particularly vulnerable to the effects of various metabolic stressors, as it is sensitive to cytotoxic glutamergic absorption or release.^[1]

CASE REPORT

In this case, a 73-year-old woman was referred to our neurology outpatient clinic with signs of amnesia. She complained of flu-like symptoms, a headache, and fatigue with a loss of appetite. She did not experience any fever, nausea, vomiting, or visual abnormalities.

The neurological examination revealed the abrupt onset of memory loss, which the patient's family reported had been evident for a few hours. She appeared with repetitive and frequent questioning and was not aware of the place and time, how she got there, or what she did immediately preceding the onset.

The brain CT and brain MRI findings did not show any abnormalities. [\[Figure 1,2,3\]](#) In the chest CT, however, bilateral areas of ground-glass opacity, consolidation, and linear opacity were observed. [\[Figure 4,5\]](#)

Her O2 saturation level was 96, and her BP was within normal ranges. In the EEG findings, sharp wave activity with a slow wave abnormality was observed. [\[Figure 6,7,8\]](#) The plasma levels of WBCs, platelets, AST, ALT, GGT, ALP, LDH, and Vitamin B12 were within the normal biochemical range. Also, the Anti-NMDA receptor antibody value was negative.

Table 1: Displays the aberrant laboratory results.

1. Lab	Value	Normal Range
CRP	49	0-5 mg/L
D-Dimer	2284	0-500 ng/L
Ferritin	429	13-150 ug/L
COVID-19 PCR	Positive	-

*Turkish Ministry of Health reference values are taken as a source.

The medication started the same day, as follows:

- Azithromycin
- Molnupiravir
- Dexamethasone
- Low-Molecular Heparin

- Levetiracetam

The next morning, she awoke alert and attuned to time and location but had no memory of the previous day. After 2 days, normal EEG findings were observed. She received hospital care for five days before being released without any issues.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

DISCUSSION

TGA is known to be a transitory state where the patient loses self-awareness. It is an "acute onset anterograde amnesia" that mostly affects the middle-aged.^[1]

It is known that patients usually don't lose self-awareness, although they are mostly unaware of the place and time, and they may appear with repetitive and frequent questioning. Repeating the same questions and sentences is common in this group of patients.

To our knowledge, the effects of the COVID-19 disease can be divided into symptoms and side effects that may or may not persist after the course of the disease. The most typical symptoms may present as flu-like symptoms, headaches, fever, cough, and anosmia; other symptoms can include diarrhea, aches and myalgias, and shortness of breath.

There are reportedly two kinds of symptoms: headache, anosmia, ageusia, and myalgia are all part of the first group. The second consists of mental disturbance and confusion. These neurological symptoms were paired with a few flu-like symptoms.

The headache complaint, however, is mostly described as "different than the previous headaches" the patients had experienced, persisting for at least seven days with a non-migraine phenotype, very intense, and distinct from prior headaches. Neurological symptoms are common and severe throughout the COVID-19 acute phase. Headaches, anosmia, and ageusia may persist after the acute stage of the illness. Women were more likely to experience the symptoms as follows: headaches, fever, sore throat, ageusia/anosmia, or myalgia. On the other hand, agitation, epileptic convulsions, and advanced age have all been linked to mental disorientation.^[7]

Many reports state "increased stress levels" as one of the triggers causing neurological symptoms in patients. Dramatic daily news on social media about the negative vaccine side effects and baseless comments are known to produce anxiety. These stress-related stimuli, including psychological and emotional stress, may cause oxidative stress, glutamate neurotoxicity, the release of vasoactive stress hormones including angiotensin I and II, and hippocampus dysfunction through a number of processes.^[8]

As for the pathophysiology of how COVID-19 disease may have caused such neurological problems, although there are no quite certain statements, some hypotheses describe this as related to RAS pathway dysfunction.

According to reports, the RAS is expressed in numerous tissues, such as the brain, liver, and reproductive organs.^[9] The amygdala is recognized as the anxiety center, and the amygdala's increased MasR receptor density may be related to ACE2's overexpression.^[10]

Angiotensin Converting Enzyme 2 (ACE2) serves as the host receptor for SARS-CoV2, the agent that causes COVID-19.^[7] In a study by "Rhodes, R. et al.", all 36 COVID-19 autopsy patients were shown to have reactive and acute inflammatory microcirculatory changes. Hypoxia, RAS dysfunction, and hypercytokinemia were among the factors previously linked to COVID-19-induced microcirculatory damage. A previous study connected endocytosed pseudovirions, which may have been produced by the SARS-CoV-2 protein and connected to vascular endothelial cells, with CNS microcirculation.^[11]

Although the true mechanism is uncertain, we experienced a case of TGA with COVID-19 disease. This is the first report related to the COVID-19 disease that presents with TGA. A 73-year-old woman showed TGA with COVID-19 syndrome, which resolved after beginning the COVID-19 medication.

CONCLUSION

This case report describes a unique presentation of COVID-19 revealed through the diagnosis of Transient Global Amnesia (TGA) in a 73-year-old woman. Initially presenting with fatigue, disorientation, and memory loss, the patient was eventually found to have COVID-19. This highlights the importance of considering COVID-19 in patients with acute neurological symptoms, even with initial negative tests. The discussion explores potential mechanisms linking COVID-19 to TGA, including stress and direct viral effects on the CNS.

This report aims to aid in the recognition and diagnosis of similar cases, expanding the understanding of COVID-19's diverse manifestations.

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